

REVEALING THE SECRET OF “GROOVE” SINGING: ANALYSIS OF J-POP MUSIC

Masaru Arai, Tastuya Matoba

formerly at Kwansei Gakuin University

{riviera314,mtb.toya0403}@gmail.com

Mitsuyo Hashida

Soai University

hashida@soai.ac.jp

Haruhiro Katayose

Kwansei Gakuin University

katayose@kwansei.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

In music, “groove” refers to the sense of rhythmic “feel” or swing. Groove, which was originally introduced to describe the taste of a band’s rhythm section, has been expanded to non-rhythmic sections and to several genres and has become a key facet of popular music. Some studies have analyzed groove by investigating the delicate beat nuances of playing the drums. However, the nature of groove that is found in continuous sound has not yet been elucidated. To describe the nature of groove, we conducted an evaluative study using a questionnaire and balance method based on signal processing for vocal melodies sung by a professional popular music vocalist. We found that the control over (voiced) consonants followed by vowels constitutes an expression that is crucial to groove in J-pop vocal melodies. The experimental results suggest that time-prolongation and pitch overshoot added to voiced consonants made listeners perceive the vowels that follow to be more accentuated, eventually enhancing listeners’ perceptions of groove elements in vocal melodies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rhythm of some types of music causes listeners to tap their feet and dance. This feeling is commonly referred to as groove and has a strong affective component as well as a strong correlation with music appreciation [1]. Groove originally represented a taste for performance expression commonly found in jazz rhythm sections; it has since been established as a form of rhythmic expression found in various forms of popular music such as salsa, funk, rock, fusion and soul.

Previous studies have provided a strong consensus on the definition of groove [1,2], and some researchers have quantitatively analyzed rhythmic performances [3–8]. Okudaira et al. [3,4] analyzed onset timing and the loudness of snare drum beats and reported that a micro-difference in onset timing effectively expresses groove. Madison et al. [6] followed this finding with an observation that tempo alone cannot explain groove, and they suggested that the main physical correlate of groove is syncopation [8]. Sioros et al. examined listeners’ experiences of groove when exposed

to synthesized musical stimuli covering a range of syncopation levels and densities of musical events [9].

Furthermore, the ideology of groove for rhythm sections has recently been expanded to continuous sound expression through melodic instruments, including vocal singing. Currently, singing voice information processing is developing considerably [10], and production software such as VOCALOID¹ is found worldwide. New technologies for vocal expression serve as methods and tools to elaborate parameters of acoustic and melodic expression such as pitch, loudness, vibrato, portamento, and joint vowels and consonants [11–14]. However, the control method for the expression of “groove” singing remains obscure and underdeveloped.

In this paper, we aimed to determine which properties of vocal singing affect groove sensation. We recorded songs with and without groove elements sung by a professional singer who can intentionally control groove expression, and we then analyzed and modified several parameters of the recordings. Section 2 describes our approach to groove analysis and general information on our analysis. In Section 3, we describe our analysis of the onset timing of voiced consonants. Section 4 describes two listening experiments that focus on the “overshoot” technique, a pitch control feature of singing.

2. GROOVE SINGING ANALYSIS APPROACH

“Groove” is a musical term related to rhythm expression. “Groove,” which was originally used to refer to the nuances of a rhythm section, now refers to singing skill and especially to pop music vocalists. It is not difficult for humans to distinguish “groove” singing from “Non-groove” singing. However, the properties of singing that make us feel that vocals have “groove” have not yet been elucidated.

To address this problem, we compared singing with and without “groove” elements sung by a professional J-pop vocalist and estimated vocal properties that may affect “groove.” From this procedure, we found that control over consonant preceding vowels is a crucial property of “groove” singing. As a result of this procedure, we find control of consonant preceding vowels is one of the crucial properties of “groove” singing. We then investigated the effects of the lengthening and pitch overshoot of voiced consonants on the expression of “groove” singing.

¹<http://www.vocaloid.com/en/>

Figure 1. Musical notes and F0 dynamics from [15]

2.1 Target Pieces and Recording

The music selected for the experiment needed to express groovy taste. Therefore, two type of music were selected: **Piece A** is “La La La Love Song²,” a middle tempo R&B and **Piece B** is “Love Rain (Koi no Ame)³,” a slow ballad composed by Japanese singer Toshinobu Kubota, who is known as one of the best singers of soul music in Japan.

We recorded and analyzed pieces A and B with and without “groove” elements, which were sung by a professional pop vocalist who is also an experienced vocal trainer of Japanese professional pop music vocalists.

2.2 Vocal Manipulation Tool

During the listening test, singing materials with properties that may affect “groove” are controlled. For this goal, we adopted STRAIGHT [13, 14], a tool that is capable of manipulating voice quality, timbre, pitch, speed and other attributes for research on speech and synthesis. The STRAIGHT tool can be used to control the length and pitch of any phoneme. An example of a pitch analysis using STRAIGHT is shown in Figure Figure 1 [15]. This figure shows that the naturalness of singing involves pitch transitions (e.g., overshoot, undershoot and vibrato).

2.3 Comparison of Onset Timing

Most “groove” studies have analyzed drum beats. Thus, onset of drum beat timing is regarded as a crucial property that causes listeners to experience “groove.” Based on prior investigations, we first compared the onset timing of vocal melody beats between expressions with and without “groove.” The effects of properties of temporal control emerging from the comparison were examined through listening experiments.

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=prfepwJ5wZE>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KuMD-Fu1T5s>

Figure 2. Histogram of deviation in consonant and vowel onset in human singing (Piece A)

2.4 Analysis Focused on Voiced Consonants

Our preliminary analysis on the onset timing of vocal notes suggested that there was no significant difference between attacks among conditions with and without “groove.” Rather than attacks, the analysis suggested that the lengthening of consonants preceding vowels may be a property of “groove” singing. From this finding, we conducted a more detailed analysis of controls by timing phonemes and separating vowels from consonants. Then, another experiment was conducted to verify whether the pitch overshoot of voiced consonants preceding vowels may also constitute a property of “groove” singing.

3. COMPARISON OF ONSET TIMING

This section compares the onset timing of consonants and vowels in vocals with and without “groove” elements and presents an estimation of crucial property candidates of “groove” singing.

3.1 Analysis of Vowel and Consonant Start Times

The lyrics of the target pieces used in our experiments are written in Japanese. Japanese belongs to the ‘mora’ language, whereby each phoneme includes a consonant and vowel. We first analyzed deviations between vowel start times and those of preceding consonants.

Figure 2 shows histograms of the start times of vowels and preceding consonants. In this figure, the start time of each phoneme is normalized, as the start time of a vowel is zero when the vowel starts at its nominal beat time. This figure suggests that vowels sung by skilled vocalists are pronounced accurately on beat time, and there are no significant differences between such features among songs sung with and without “groove” conditions. By contrast, the onset of consonants under “groove” conditions occurs earlier than under “non-groove” conditions. These results suggest that maintaining the tempo of vowels is a funda-

mental skill of rhythmic expression, and other properties are used to positively express “groove” singing.

Figure 3. Histogram of consonant onset in human singing (Piece A)

Figure 3 shows histograms of consonant lengths, which are divided more precisely. This figure shows that the lengths of nasal and brush consonants are lengthened. That is, some nasal consonants are intentionally lengthened compared with other consonants in “groove” singing.

To verify that this control affects “groove” singing, we recorded “groove” and “non-groove” singing samples whereby all consonants were replaced with “m,” and we then compared these samples with the original recordings.

Figure 4 shows the results of this comparison, where the same procedure as shown in Figure 2 was adopted for analysis. When comparing Figure 4 with 2, “m,” is pronounced earlier than other consonants. When comparing “groove” and “non-groove” features in Figure 4, there is variance in the starting time where “m” is pronounced sooner and for a longer period in “groove” songs than in “non-groove” songs. Averages and variances of start times ahead of the nominal beat time of “m” were, $91[ms]$ and $1,651[ms^2]$ for “groove” songs and $76[ms]$ and $961[ms^2]$ for “non-groove” songs. The start time of “m” in “groove” songs was found to occur much earlier than that in “non-groove” songs ($P < 0.05$).

3.2 Listening Experiment

This section describes an experiment conducted to investigate the effects of consonant and vowel onset timing on “groove” sensation from a psychological point of view. In the experiment, participants were asked to state which song they felt exhibited more “groove,” using Scheffe’s paired comparison based on eight sound materials (see Table 1). Each consonant and vowel was replaced to simulate “groove” and “non-groove” conditions using STRAIGHT, as shown in Figure 5. Melodies for this part of the experiment were selected from those including conjunct motion, disjunct motion, and same-pitch transitions between two adjacent notes in Song B based on the implication and realization

Figure 4. Histogram of deviation in vowel and consonant onset in consonant-controlled singing (Piece A). All consonants are replaced with “m.”

Phrase No.	Human singing	Consonant length	Vowel onset
a	groove	groove	groove
b	groove	groove	non-groove
c	groove	non-groove	groove
d	groove	non-groove	non-groove
e	non-groove	groove	groove
f	non-groove	groove	non-groove
g	non-groove	non-groove	groove
h	non-groove	non-groove	non-groove

Table 1. Phrase listening stimuli patterns

Figure 5. Manipulation of sound materials using STRAIGHT

model proposed by Eugene Narmour [16].

Thirty-six individuals participated in this experiment (male: 28, female: 8). Among them, 24 reported having experience with music. All the participants selected either the originally recorded “groove” sample or a consonant stimulus that was replaced with that of the originally recorded “groove” sample, as the “groove” stimulus. This result

Figure 6. Procedural overview of the F0 transition analysis

suggests that listeners judge “groove” taste based on singing while listening for consonant control features.

3.3 Discussion

No major differences were found in the pronunciation of vowels in songs with and without “groove” conditions. Nevertheless, listeners participating in the experiment noted that they heard vowels with “groove” elements (i.e., consonants that are pronounced earlier and that are more accentuated). This finding suggests that auditory illusions induced by control over preceding consonants may be a central facet of “groove” singing. In the following section, we explore our more detailed experiments that focused on the pitch control of nasal consonants in “groove” singing.

4. ANALYSIS OF VOICED CONSONANT PITCH CONTROL

This section describes two experiments that were conducted to investigate effects of pitch control on groove sensation.

As noted in Section 3, we hypothesized that auditory illusion brought about by the pitch control of voiced consonants may accentuate subsequent vowels. We also found that the control of voiced consonants, and especially pitch overshoot during melodic leap progression, may be a key property of groove singing.

We thus conducted a listening experiment to investigate how the pitch control of voiced consonants of sequential and leap progression affects the loudness of subsequent vowels. We then investigated how this control may increase “groove” features of a phrase.

4.1 Voice Synthesis for the Experiments

To analyze and resynthesize the pitch control of voiced consonants, we adopted a pitch transition model that was proposed by Ohishi et al.: models human pitch control based on human physical constraints [17]. This model enables us to control natural pitch transitions including overshoots and undershoots with variables ζ and Ω , respectively, as shown in Figure 6. We analyzed an F0 sequence of voiced consonants and vowels to resynthesize songs in which the parameters changed, and we conducted a listening experiment with the resynthesized singing.

4.1.1 Note-level division of audio signals using HMM

First, the F0 sequence of singing o_{Hz} is converted to logscale frequency o_{cent} as follows:

$$o_{cent} = 1200 \log_2 \frac{o_{Hz}}{440 \times 2^{\frac{3}{12} - 5}} \quad (1)$$

We assume that the pitch transition follows the Elgodic Hidden-Markov Model (eHMM). In the eHMM, there are 42 states that correspond to a pitch of 700 cents from 3000 to 7000 cents. The output of each state appears as a normal distribution where the average is the frequency of pitch and the variance is 100. The self-transition possibility is 0.9, and the transition possibility for other states is 0.1/41. Thus, the F0 sequence is finally divided into a musical notes after the route estimation of each state through a Viterbi search.

4.1.2 Least-Squares Fitting

Next, we estimate parameters of transfer functions using fitting procedures for the dynamic component.

$$H(s) = \frac{\Omega^2}{s^2 + 2\zeta\Omega s + \Omega^2} \quad (2)$$

As in pre-processing, F0 transitions of each note is normalized as follows:

1. The F0 sequence of a phrase is initialized at zero from the beginning note of a phrase,
2. If a note is NOT positioned at the beginning of a phrase, the F0 sequence of the note is subtracted from the beginning frequency and from the frequency of the preceding note.

The last step is to estimate the parameters ζ and Ω so that the sum of squares of the residuals between the F0 sequence and signal convolved with the impulse response of the transfer function is minimized.

Parameters obtained through this procedure enables us to analyze and synthesize F0 dynamics for each note.

4.2 Exp. 1: Relationship between Pitch Overshoot and Loudness

The first experiment is conducted to verify that the pitch-overshoot of voiced consonants causes listeners to feel that a note includes a louder consonant.

4.2.1 Voice Data

The experimental stimuli are pairs of six phrases derived from Pieces A and B with an overshoot that is significantly different between human groove and non-groove songs. A pair of singing data for each phrase was set up as follows:
[x] non-groove human singing
[y] overshoot-amplified singing— an overshoot of [x] was amplified to the same degree as that in the human groove song.

	$x < y$	$x >= y$	Total
Expected number	36	72	108
Observed number	55	53	108

Table 2. Comparison between amplified pitch-overshoot and loudness: (x) non-groove human singing and (y) overshoot-amplified singing

4.2.2 Procedure

The above voices were randomly shuffled [x-y, y-x, x-x]. Six students in their early twenties compared the loudness of all 18 patterns in the pairs of songs over 6 phrases. They then reported which was louder (i.e., the first, the second, or both were the same).

4.2.3 Results

Table 2 shows the results. From 108 answers, we obtained 55 answers that support our hypothesis. $x < y$ means that the overshoot-amplified note was perceived as louder than the non-groove note. We expected 36 answers to be consistent with the hypothesis. The χ^2 test results are significant at the 5% level. This result suggests that pitch-overshoot controls perceptions of loudness. Moreover, the $x >= y$ answers only account for 10% of the $x >= y$ answers.

4.3 Exp. 2: Comparison between Amplified Pitch Overshoot and Groove Sensation

The second experiment was conducted to verify whether pitch overshoot consonants increase groove features of a phrase.

4.3.1 Voice Data

As in the previous experiment, pairs of songs with the six phrases in Pieces A and B were prepared.

[x] non-groove human singing

[y] overshoot-amplified singing— ALL overshoots in the phrase were amplified to the same degree as those of the human groove songs.

4.3.2 Procedure

Then, 10 listeners used a web interface for the experiment. Participants listened to the twelve phrases at random through headphones or a loud speaker system in a quiet room, and they then reported degrees of groove sensation based on a 10-step system (0-9). They then described their judgment criteria.

4.3.3 Results

Figure 7 shows the listening experiment results. The horizontal axis represents the phrase number, and the vertical axis represents the average of the degree of the groove evaluation. For all of the phrases, overshoot-amplified songs presented a higher degree of groove sensation than human non-groove songs. Differences between phrases except for those related to Phrase No. 5 were significant at 5% according to the t test.

Figure 7. Amplified pitch overshoot and groove sensation listening results

This result shows that pitch overshoot control affects groove perception.

4.4 Discussion

As shown in Table 2, pitch overshoot amplification in non-groove songs made listeners experience these songs as louder. In particular, only 10% of the respondents experienced overshoot amplified songs as softer in volume. This finding suggests that there is a positive correlation between pitch overshoot and loudness perception. Moreover, one listener commented that he felt that the singer of the overshoot amplified song sang with a more pronounced accent and at a faster speed. This result supports our hypothesis that loudness is sensed more in overshoot songs even when volumes between songs are identical in practice.

As shown in Figure 7, overshoot amplified phrases were ascribed higher degrees of groove sensation than human non-groove phrases, and the five phrases were significantly different. This result suggests that amplifying pitch overshoot in a voiced consonant induces groove sensation. Several participants also commented on loudness as the listening criteria (e.g., accentuation of the start of a word). Such comments show that the perceived loudness of voiced consonants through pitch-overshoot control can either induce “groove” elements in vowels or not.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

As described in Section 3, in regards to the onset timing of vowels on beat, there are no differences between songs with and without “groove.” The main difference between songs with and without “groove” is the length of preceding consonants and especially of voiced consonants such as “m” or “n”. A lengthened voiced consonant causes listeners to sense feel a more powerful “groove.” Our interpretation of this result is that pronouncing vowels on beat is indispensable for expressing accurate rhythm and that auditory illusions yielded through the control of consonants are used to express “groove.” The experiment described in Section 4 was conducted to confirm this hypothesis. The results show that pitch overshoot in addition to the length of voiced consonants preceding vowels causes listeners to feel a more powerful “groove” elements. We also found that pitch overshoot of a voiced consonant preceding a vowel causes listeners to feel that a vowel is being sung louder. These results suggest that variations in

the perceived loudness of vowels stimulate “groove” sensation.

To summarize the above results, the onset timing and intensity of vowels are not essential for expressing “groove.” Accuracy is given priority as a means of expressing fundamental vocal skill. Voiced consonant lengthening and pitch-overshoot are adopted to create an auditory illusion of an accentuated vowel following a voiced consonant.

Our findings reflect experiments that were conducted based on Japanese pop. Our findings may thus only apply to J-pop, which is characterized by lyrics written in mora languages. However, we believe the findings can be generalized, as they were interpreted based on perceptions of auditory illusions caused by a combination of a consonant and a vowel forming a phoneme, which are not tied to any particular language. We would like to conduct more experiments based on Korean pop, which is written in another mora language, and on American pop to identify the secrets of “groove” in terms of vocal melody.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to Dr. Ryuichi Nariyama and Dr. Shuichi Matsumoto of Yamaha for their assistance in this study. This study was partially funded through a Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (C) [15K02126].

6. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Madison, “Experiencing groove induced by music: Consistency and phenomenology,” *Music Perception*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 201–208, 2006.
- [2] P. Janata, S. T. Tomic, and J. M. Haberman, “Sensorimotor coupling in music and the psychology of the groove,” *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, vol. 141, no. 1, pp. 54–75, Feb. 2012.
- [3] K. Okudaira, K. Hirata, and H. Katayose, “Relationship between ‘groove feeling’ and the timing and loudness of drum attacks in popular music,” *IPSJ SIG Technical Report*, vol. 2005-MUS-59, pp. 27–32, 2004.
- [4] K. Okudaira, K. Hirata, and H. Katayose, “Relationship between ‘groove feeling’ and the timing and loudness of drum attacks in popular music (3rd report): Fundamental analysis of drum performance data and implementation of drum performance rendering system,” *IPSJ SIG Technical Report*, vol. 2006-MUS-64, pp. 53–58, 2006.
- [5] M. Wright and E. Beradahl, “Towards machine learning of expressive microtiming in brazilian drumming,” in *Proceedings of International Compute Music Conference*, 2006.
- [6] G. Madison, F. Gouyon, F. Ullen, and K. Hornstrm, “Modeling the tendency for music to induce movement in humans: first correlations with low-level audio descriptors across music genres,” *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 1578–1594, Oct. 2011.
- [7] J. Fruhauf, R. Kopiez, and F. Platz, “Music on the timing grid: The influence of microtiming on the perceived groove quality of a simple drum pattern performance,” *Musicae Scientiae*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 246–269, 2013.
- [8] G. Madison and G. Sioros, “What musicians do to induce the sensation of groove in simple and complex melodies, and how listeners perceive it,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 5, no. 894, Aug. 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00894>
- [9] G. Sioros, M. Miron, M. Davies, F. Gouyon, and G. Madison, “Syncopation creates the sensation of groove in synthesized music examples,” *Frontiers in psychology*, vol. 5, Sep. 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01036>
- [10] M. Goto, “Singing information processing,” in *Proceedings of the 12th IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing (IEEE ICSP 2014)*, October 2014, pp. 2431–2438.
- [11] T. Nakano, M. Goto, and Y. Hiraga, “An automatic singing skill evaluation method for unknown melodies,” *Journal of Information Processing Society of Japan*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 227–236, Jan. 2007.
- [12] T. Nakano and M. Goto, “Vocalistner2: A singing synthesis system able to mimic a user’s singing in terms of voice timbre changes as well as pitch and dynamics,” in *Proceedings of the 2011 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP 2011)*, May 2011, pp. 453–456.
- [13] H. Kawahara, T. Irino, and M. Morise, “An interference-free representation of instantaneous frequency of periodic signals and its application to f0 extraction,” in *Proc. ICASSP 2011*, May 2011, pp. 5420–5423.
- [14] M. Morise, “An attempt to develop a singing synthesizer by collaborative creation,” in *Proc. the Stockholm Music Acoustics Conference 2013 (SMAC2013)*, Stockholm, 2013, pp. 287–292.
- [15] T. Saitou, N. Tsuji, M. Unoki, and M. Akagi, “Analysis of acoustic features affecting “singing-ness” and its application to singing-voice synthesis from speaking-voice,” in *Proc. Inter Speech - ICSLP*, 2004.
- [16] E. Narmour, *The analysis and cognition of melodic complexity: the implication-realization model*. University of Chicago Press, 1992.
- [17] Y. Ohishi, H. Kameoka, D. Mochihashi, and K. Kashino, “A stochastic model of singing voice f0 contours for characterizing expressive dynamic components,” in *proc. international conference on spoken language processing*, in *INTERSPEECH 2012*, Sep 2012.